

IGNAZ PHILIPP SEMMELWEIS ON COMMEMORATIVE MEDALS

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Annotation

The article presents new materials of the study, dedicated to the reflection in the media of medal art and numismatics of the memory of the famous obstetrician Igna Philipp Semmelweis. This article is a logical continuation of the author's earlier articles, which presented the history of life, professional and scientific feats of life, which lived in the era of the Austro-Hungarian Empire and made a global contribution to asepsis and antiseptic, as well as the prevention of postpartum septic complications in pregnant women and puerpera.

Keywords: Ignaz Philipp Semmelweis, numismatics, commemorative medals.

Introduction

The writing of this article was facilitated by the receipt of new research results concerning the reflection of the memory of the famous Austro-Hungarian obstetrician Ignacy Semmelweis in collecting means and, first of all, in medal art. From early childhood, my late father introduced me to the wonderful world of collecting. And this impulse has not left me for almost 60 years of my life. In the last 20 years, I have been drawn to studying the issue of reflection in philately, numismatics, faleristics, and other types of collecting, as the history of medicine and its heroes. Studying the scientific and medical feat of I.F. Semmelweis (1818-1865), both by me personally and in collaboration with a famous collector and author of a number of serious articles on medal art, incl. in medicine and biology, Viktor Yuryevich Barshtein [1]. articles were written, there were also sections concerning the contribution of I.F. Semmelweis in asepsis and antiseptic, and his revolutionary approach to eliminating "childbed fever", which in the past claimed thousands of lives of women giving birth [1-3]. This scientific research, author's article is devoted to the preservation and enhancement, of historical memory, of the famous Austro-Hungarian obstetrician-gynecologist, Ignaz Philipp Semmelweis, in numismatics, in the reflection of a number of commemorative, thematic, tabletop medals, with their image, as in the obverse, and in reverse, and accompanying these illustrations screenshot copies, accompanying texts.

Aim of Study

The purpose of this article is to present and analyze the results of the research conducted by the author, dedicated to the study of the issue of reflecting the historical memory of Ignaz Philipp Semmelweis, in the reflection of such a collecting tool as numismatics, on thematic, commemorative tabletop medals, presented in a screenshot copy, as illustrations in the accompanying text of this article.

Hypothesis of the Study

In the process of preparing for the writing of this research article, its author put forward a working hypothesis, the essence of which is as follows: the author of the study suggested that in a number of collecting means and, in

particular, in numismatics, on commemorative tabletop medals, there may be presented as portraits of I.F. Semmelweis, as well as a number of historical stories dedicated to his life and his scientific feat.

Research Objectives

1. Find. both on the Internet and in other sources, the necessary materials, are thematically related to the memory, life, and scientific activities of Ignaz Philipp Semmelweis.
2. Select all found illustrative and numismatic materials (commemorative table medals) dedicated to the life and scientific work of this scientist.
3. Systematization and analysis of the received material, with the aim of writing your own, author's, research article based on these materials.

Material and Methods

When writing this research article, its author actively used research methods such as literary critical analysis of all available, at the time of this research, both domestic and foreign literature, thematically related to the research being conducted; Internet materials and, in particular, special sites, both scientific and special sites of collectors, on which articles dedicated to the memory of I.F. were studied. Semmelweis, his life of scientific activity, as well as numismatic materials, in the form of commemorative table medals dedicated to the memory of the scientist [1-49].

Results and Discussion

In the last year, when studying available sources of information, I discovered a lot of collection materials that I had not previously presented in articles. Now, I would like to introduce them to dear readers. So, in Fig. 1, the obverse and reverse show an Austrian commemorative gold medal (Au, 585), dedicated to the 150th anniversary of the death of I. F. Semmelweis [4, 5]. On the obverse of this medal, in its upper part, in a circle, there is an inscription in German "150. TODESNAG IGNAZ SEMMELWEIS. 1865", which translated means "150 years since the death of Ignaz Semmelweis. 1865". The author's mark is at the bottom. The word "HYGIENA" is also written in Latin. In the center, in the circle on the left, there is a portrait of a

scientist, turned to the right. In the center of the obverse of the medal, dividing it in half, the staff of Asclepius entwined with a snake is depicted, and to the right of it is shown the scene of hand washing before childbirth, which was proposed and actively introduced into practice by I.F. Semmelweis [4, 5]. On the reverse of the medal, large, in the center, there is a double-headed eagle, like the coat of arms of Austria, under it there are 2 capital letters of the

German alphabet “A” and “R” - “Republic of Austria”. Along the entire edge of the reverse, there is an inscription in German “GOLD AUS OSTERREUCH” - “Gold from Austria” and a similar expression in English “AURUM AUSTRIAE”. There are also 2 hallmarks indicating that the material from which this medal is made is 585 gold [4, 5].

Figure 1. Austrian gold medal dedicated to I.F. Semmelweis

Figure 2. Commemorative bronze medal dedicated to I.F. Semmelweis

Fig: 2 A commemorative bronze medal dedicated to the scientist is presented. On the obverse of the medal is a portrait of the scientist, turned to the right, as well as the dates of his life and the full spelling of his first and last name. The reverse of the medal contains a stylized image of a powerful naked man

carrying a lit torch in front of him, in his outstretched right hand, and in his left hand holding a large book, between the pages of which there is a large snake squeezed by them, wrapping its body around a walking man [6].

Figure 3. Commemorative Hungarian medal, depicting I.F. Semmelweis

Fig: 3 Obverse and reverse, presents a commemorative Hungarian bronze medal dedicated to I.F. Semmelweis and the Budapest Medical University, which bears his name. Its obverse features a head portrait of a scientist, facing to the right. Along the entire contour of the obverse of the medal, from left to right, there is the inscription “VNIVERSITAS MEDICINAE “SEMMEWEIS” “BUDAPESTINI” in a stylized font. The date “1951-1976” is indicated under the portrait. On the reverse of the medal, in its center is the building of the Budapest Medical University, and under its image is the inscription “ANNVS. FVNDATIONIS FACVLTATIS.MEDICINAE. BUDAPESTINENSIS. 1760” [7].

The next commemorative bronze medal dedicated to I.F. Semmelweis, is interesting because in its plot, presented on the obverse, an image is given of I.F.

Semmelweis is interesting because in its plot, presented on the obverse, an image is given of I.F. himself. Semmelweis washing his hands in a bowl before giving birth to a woman in labor, as well as an image of another

famous doctor, Oliver W. Holmes, standing at the bed of a woman giving birth, cared for by a midwife. This scene is framed by inscriptions in English. At the bottom, along the lower pole of the obverse, the surnames of the doctors are “HOLMES – SEMMELWEIS”, and at the top - “SAFETY IN CHILDBIRTH”, which translates as “Safety in childbirth” [8]. The reverse of the medal is divided vertically into 2 unequal parts. On the left, the smaller part of the reverse is decorated with an image of the staff of Asclepius entwined with a snake. On the right, most part of the reverse bears inscriptions about doctors. At the top, first, there is an inscription in English: “O.W. HOLMES. 1818-1894” and “I.P. SEMMELWEIS. 1818-1865”. Just below is the text in English: “Their Insight Revealed the Way by Which Puerperal Fever Could Be Eliminated”, which translates as “Their Understanding Showed the Way by Which Puberate Fever Can be Eliminated” [8].

Figure 4. Commemorative medal in honor of I.F. Semmelweis and O.V. Holmes

Figure 5. Commemorative bronze medal dedicated to I.F. Semmelweis

Fig: 5. Presented, in obverse and reverse, a bronze Hungarian medal dedicated to the memory of I.F. Semmelweis [9]. On its obverse, large, in the center, there is a portrait of a scientist, slightly turned to the right. The portrait, on the left, is bordered by the dates of the scientist's life "1818 – 1865", and on the left, there is the spelling of his first and last name

"SEMMEIWEIS IGNAZ". The reverse of the medal, in the center, is decorated with the inscription in capital calligraphic letters in Latin "Pro salute hominum", which translates as "For the health of people", and a beautiful calligraphic monogram [9].

Figure 6. Commemorative medal dedicated to I.F. Semmelweis

Fig: 6. A commemorative silver Austrian medal dedicated to I.F. is presented. Semmelweis [10]. Its obverse, large in the center, is decorated with a portrait of a doctor, turned to the right, surrounded by his first and last name "SEMMEIWEIS IGNAZ", and below - the dates of the scientist's life "1818 - 1865", with a laurel branch to the left of the dates of his life. On the reverse

of this medal, in its center, there is a building with columns and the signature under it "PORTAL AN HAUPTGE BAUDE". Along the edge of the entire reverse, there is an inscription in German "SEMMEIWEIS MEININGEN MEDIZINISCHE FACHSCHULE", which translates as "Semmelweis Medical School in Meiningen" [10].

Figure 7. Commemorative Hungarian medal dedicated to I.F. Semmelweis

Fig: 7. Presented, in obverse and reverse, another Hungarian bronze commemorative medal dedicated to I.F. Semmelweis. On its obverse, large, in the center there is a portrait of the famous doctor, facing left. On the left of the portrait is the inscription "SEMMEIWEIS. IGNAZ", and on the right "FÜLÖP – 1818 – 1865". On the reverse of the medal, occupying almost its entire area, a kneeling defeated, and dying Aesculapius is depicted, bitten by

a snake in his left hand, and holding in his right hand an extinguishing torch bent to the ground. To the left of the picture is the inscription in Hungarian "ÉLETEKÉRT", and to the right "ÉLETET", which means "For life - life" [1-3, 11]. This drawing can probably symbolize the death of I.F. Semmelweis from an injection (wound) of the hand, after working in the morgue. The scientist died from a septic complication of this wound [1-3, 11].

Figure 8. Commemorative Hungarian silver medal dedicated to I.F. Semmelweis

Continuing my story about reflecting the memory of the famous Austro-Hungarian obstetrician I.F. Semmelweis, in works of medal art [1-3], I would like to present the following selection of memorable ones, incl. and table medals dedicated to this famous person. Considering that this famous doctor lived and worked in the then Austro-Hungarian Empire, in clinics in Budapest and Vienna, these two, now independent sovereign countries, dispute his affiliation and, accordingly, fame. Therefore, it is not surprising that the largest amount of collection materials, including commemorative medals dedicated to I.F. Semmelweis, was released by Hungary [1-3].

Fig: 8. Obverse and reverse, shows a silver commemorative medal minted in honor of this great physician. On the obverse, large, in the center is his

portrait, facing right. Along the edge of the obverse, from left to right, are its data written in Hungarian “SEMMELEWEIS IGNAČZ FULOP. 1818-1865”. The reverse of the medal depicts a stylized image of a man standing on one knee and holding a large book above/behind his head, with which he intends to hit/kill a huge snake entwined around his legs and preparing to bite this man. To the left of the man’s torso are the Roman numerals MCMXVIII, and along the edge of the reverse there is an inscription in Latin “POTUIT. RERUM. COGNOSCERE. FELIX. QUI. QUOD. AMAI. DEFENDER” which translates as “The man who recognized the defender”[12].

Figure 9. Commemorative Hungarian silver medal dedicated to I.F. Semmelweis

Fig: 9 Shows a commemorative Hungarian silver medal, from the “Greats of Our People” series, entitled “Savior of Mothers - Ignaz Semmelweis / God Bless the Hungarians!” Its mass is 10.37 g, diameter is 35 mm [13]. On the obverse of this medal, there is a composition representing the image of a half-

length portrait of I.F. Semmelweis, and just behind him, an image of a mother bending over her newborn child and kissing him. The reverse of the medal is decorated with the image of the small and large coats of arms of Hungary [13].

Figure 10. Commemorative bronze Hungarian medal dedicated to I.F. Semmelweis

Fig: 10 Shows another Hungarian, commemorative bronze, one-sided medal dedicated to I.F. Semmelweis. On its obverse, there is a very large portrait of a doctor, with a slight half-turn of the face to the right. Clockwise, to the right and left of the portrait, his data is written in Hungarian, including the dates

of his life “SEMMELEWEIS IGNAČZ FULOP. 1818-1865” [14]. The author of this medal is I.F. Semmelweis Jozsef Remenyi. Single-sided, cast bronze medal, size 100 mm. The name of this medal is “SEMMELEWEIS MEDICAL UNIVERSITY / SEMMELEWEIS IGNAČ / MEMORIAL MEDICINE” [14]

Figure 11. Commemorative Hungarian bronze medal dedicated to I.F. Semmelweis

The next Hungarian, commemorative bronze medal (author: Reményi József), dedicated to I.F. Semmelweis, in obverse and reverse, is presented in **Fig: 11**. Its obverse represents the head portrait of the great doctor, facing left. On the reverse of the medal, in close-up, there is a symbolic plot in which a man (the god Asclepius), standing on his left knee, and holding a snake in

his left hand by the neck, near the head, pacifies it by thrusting a burning torch into the snake's open mouth, which he (man/god), held in his right, outstretched hand. Around the depicted scene, from left to right, there are the doctor's data written in Hungarian "SEMMELEIS IGNÁCZ FÜLÖP. 1818-1865". The diameter of this medal is 71 mm [15].

Figure 12. Commemorative medal dedicated to I.F. Semmelweis

Fig: 12. Is a one-sided white metal medal dedicated to I.F. Semmelweis, one of the "youngest" medals (2008) dedicated to this doctor. It was released on the 190th anniversary of his birth. The author of this medal is Guttler, Peter Götz. To the right of his half-length portrait is a symbol of medicine, a snake entwining the staff of Asclepius, the doctor's data in German "IGNAZ PHIL. SEMMELWEIS. *1.7.1818 – †13.8.1865" and the inscription in German

"1847. ERKANNT D. INFEKTIOSE URSAUM DEAKINDBETT-FIBERS U.", and further "BEWARTHE SO DAS LEBEN D. MUTTER FÜR IHRE KINDER", which translates as "A FAMOUS WINNER OF INFECTIOUS PARENTAL FEVER" and "WAIT LIKE A MOTHER'S LIFE FOR THEIR CHILDREN." The diameter of the medal is 93 mm [16].

Figure 13. Award medal from Semmelweis University in Budapest

Fig: 13. Shows the bronze medal of the Semmelweis Medical University in Budapest, which the University Senate annually awards to each outstanding physician for the advancement of Hungarian medical science and in recognition of his scientific work at a high level. The Semmelweis Medal can be awarded not only to an employee of the Semmelweis Medical University but also to medical personnel at other universities and medical institutions

[17]. The obverse of this medal, in the center, is decorated with a portrait of a doctor, and information about him, in Hungarian "SEMMELEIS IGNÁC. 1818-1865". The reverse of this medal is an image of the main building of the medical university in Budapest, and the inscription above it, at the top, "SEMMELEIS EGYETEM", which translates as "SEMMELEIS UNIVERSITY" [17].

Figure 14. Commemorative medal of the American-Hungarian Medical Association with the image of I.F. Semmelweis

The commemorative, award, a gold-plated metal medal (Semmelweis Medal), **Fig: 14**, obverse and reverse, is an insignia and award of the American-Hungarian Medical Association (Semmelweis Scientific Society). It is awarded to full members of the Semmelweis Scientific Society. The obverse of this medal is a head portrait of I.F. Semmelweis, and an inscription in Hungarian with his data, going counterclockwise, from left to right

"SEMMELEIS IGNÁC. 1818-1865". The reverse of this medal, in the center, is decorated with the image of the Biblical scene of Adam and Eve standing at the foot of the Tree of Good and Evil in the Garden of Eden. To the right and left of the picture, there are inscriptions in English "AMERICAN-HUNGARIAN MEDICAL ASSOCIATION. 1926-1951" [18]

Figure 15. Commemorative medal dedicated to I.F. Semmelweis

Fig: 15. Shows another Hungarian commemorative bronze medal. Its obverse features a head portrait of a doctor, facing left and an inscription in Hungarian “SEMMELEIS IGNACZ FÜLÖP. 1818-1865”. The reverse of the medal represents an image of a naked young mother sitting on 4 large books, holding

a baby in her outstretched arms. Along the edge of the reverse, there is an inscription in Hungarian “AZ ANYÁK MEG-MENT TÖJE”, which translates as “Savior of Mothers” [19].

Figure 16. Commemorative Hungarian medal with a portrait of I.F. Semmelweis

Continuing my story about reflecting the memory of the famous Austro-Hungarian obstetrician I.F. Semmelweis, in works of medal art [1-3], in this part of the article about him, I would like to present the following selection of memorable ones, incl. and table medals dedicated to this famous person.

Fig: 16. A commemorative Hungarian one-sided bronze medal is presented. It is awarded to the authors of the best scientific papers in medicine at the

University of Budapest. The diameter of the medal is 92 cm. On the reverse of this medal, there is a portrait of the scientist, half-turned to the right. To the right, along the edge of the portrait, the name of the scientist “SEMMELEIS” is written. Authors of this medal: Ifj. Pál Mihály and B. Szabó Edit [20].

Figure 17. Commemorative Hungarian medal with a portrait of I.F. Semmelweis

Fig: 17 Shows another bronze Hungarian, one-sided commemorative medal, on the obverse of which there is a portrait of the scientist, with a slight half turn to the right. Along the upper edge of the obverse of the medal, from left to right, in Hungarian, there is an inscription of his name, surname, and dates

of life: “SEMMELEIS IGNAC. 1818-1865”. The author of this medal, which is part of a large series of medals (69 pieces) dedicated to famous people of Hungary and world science and culture, is the famous Hungarian medalist Gábor Toros [21].

Figure 18. Hungarian award medal with a portrait of I. F. Semmelweis

Fig: 18 Shows the following Hungarian commemorative, award, a bronze one-sided medal, with a portrait of I.F. Semmelweis on its obverse. The scientist's face is turned, half-turn, to the right. On the right edge of the obverse of the medal is the inscription “SEMMELEIS” and “DIJ” [22].

There is a dotted border along the edge of the medal. This medal is awarded for special merits to medical and social workers on the day of memory of I.F. Semmelweis [22].

Figure 19. Hungarian award medal, with the image of I.F. Semmelweis

The next Hungarian award bronze, a one-sided medal, is presented in obverse, in **Fig: 19**. Its obverse is decorated with the profile of the scientist, turned to the left. The dates of his life are placed above his head: “1818 –

1865” a, below. a profile portrait of the scientist – his name (abbreviated) and surname: «I. PH. SEMMELWEIS» [23].

Figure 20. Commemorative medal in honor of I.F. Semmelweis

Fig: 20. Represents a commemorative, Hungarian silver medal (2000), obverse and reverse. On the reverse of this medal, there is a portrait of the scientist, turned to the right, with an inscription on the right edge, his last

name in Hungarian: “SEMMELWEIS”. On the reverse of the medal, there is an image of the hospital where the maternity hospital was located, and the inscription «100 EVES A MISKOLCI SEMMELWEIS. KORHÁZ” [24].

Figure 21. Commemorative medal with the image of I.F. Semmelweis

Fig: 21 Shows, in obverse and reverse, a commemorative bronze medal. On its obverse, against the background of a stone wall, framed by climbing ivy, is a monument to I.F. Semmelweis holding a child in his arms. In the center of the composition, the name and surname of the scientist and the dates of his life are indicated “SEMMELWEIS IGNAC. 1818-1865”. The reverse of the medal, in the center, bears an image of the emblem, with a snake entwining

the staff of Asclepius, ending with a stylized image of an oval mirror. At the top is the abbreviation “S.I.H.M.”, and the signature below is “BUDAPEST. 1974.” Along the entire contour of the reverse of the medal there is the inscription “CONGRESSES INTERNATIONALIS XXIV HISTORIAE ARTIS MEDICINAE”, which translates as “XXIV INTERNATIONAL CONGRESS OF THE HISTORY OF THE ART OF MEDICINE” [25].

Figure 22. Commemorative medal with the image of I.F. Semmelweis

The next commemorative bronze, one-sided medal, on its obverse bears a head, profile portrait of I.F. Semmelweis, turned to the left. At the top, in a semi-arch, there is the inscription “IGNAZ PHILIPP SEMMELWEIS”, and

at the bottom - the dates of his life “1818-1865”. The medal is shown in **Fig: 22** [26].

Figure 23. Commemorative bronze medal dedicated to I.F. Semmelweis

Fig: 23 Shows a Hungarian, cast, one-sided bronze medal, with a portrait of I.F. on the obverse. Semmelweis turned to the left. To the right and left of the portrait, there is the inscription “SEMMELEWEIS IGNAC”, and below,

slightly to the right, under the portrait, the dates of his life are given as “1818-1865” [27].

Figure 24. Commemorative medal dedicated to I.F. Semmelweis

Next, presented, in obverse and reverse, is a silver Hungarian medal, with the image of a scientist. On the obverse, large, on the left side, is a bust-length portrait of I.F. Semmelweis, half turn to the right. To the right of the portrait, there is the inscription “SEMMELEWEIS IGNAC”, and under this inscription,

the dates of his life are given as “1818-1865” [28]. The reverse of the medal is decorated with a stylized floral ornament, and the inscription at the top of the reverse, in Hungarian, is “NAGY MAGYAROK”, which translates as “THE GREAT HUNGARIAN”. This medal is shown in **Fig: 24** [28].

Figure 25. Commemorative medal in honor of I.F. Semmelweis

Fig: 25 Shows, in obverse and reverse, a commemorative bronze Hungarian medal, also dedicated to I.F. Semmelweis. In the center of the obverse, large, is a portrait of I.F. Semmelweis, slightly turned to the left. Along the contour of the obverse, there is an inscription in Hungarian “EVFORDULOJARA.1968. SEMMELEWEIS IGNAC. SZULETESE 150”, which can be translated as “150th birthday anniversary”. The reverse of the

medal shows an image of a seated mother holding her child on her lap. They hold each other's hands. Along the entire edge of the reverse, there is an inscription in Hungarian “TANACS SEMMELEWEIS / ROKUS / KORHAZ. PEST MEGYEI”, which can be translated as “Teacher Semmelweis. Anniversary of the founding of the hospital” [29].

Figure 26. Commemorative medal dedicated to I. F. Semmelweis

The contribution of I.F. Semmelweis's work on the issues of asepsis and antiseptics, the reduction of maternal mortality, and postpartum septic complications is truly great and, without exaggeration, has worldwide significance. The sterile hands of a doctor - a surgeon, an obstetrician, a specialist in any other field - have long been the key to the safety of both the medical worker himself and his patient. And in this matter, I.F. Semmelweis, is a hero of medicine, the savior of mothers, as he was called at that time, and

a pioneer of the introduction of asepsis and antiseptics into medical practice [1-3; thirty; 31; [40-42]. Continuing my story about the medical feat of I.F. Semmelweis in the reflection of medal art and phaleristics, I would like to present a new selection of commemorative medals and badges with the image of I.F. Semmelweis and/or associated with his name. Thus, in **Fig: 26**, a bronze Hungarian medal issued in honor of the scientist is presented in obverse and reverse. In the center of the obverse of the medal, there is a large

depiction of Semmelweis standing, who is in the delivery room, holding in his left hand a flask with a disinfectant solution (chlorine) for treating hands. Behind him is a mother holding a baby in her arms. At the top and to the right, along the edge of the obverse of the medal, there is the inscription “AZ

ANYÁK MEGMENTŐJE - SEMMELWEIS IGNÁC - 1818-1865” or “Savior of Mothers”, dates of life “1818-1865” [32]. The reverse of the medal shows a view of Semmelweis's former school. The medal has a diameter of 42.5 mm, there are options for medals made of silver and copper [32].

Figure 27. Commemorative medal dedicated to the introduction of I.F. Semmelweis, hand washing before childbirth

Fig: 27. The obverse and reverse show a Hungarian commemorative bronze medal, on the obverse of which there is a chest-length portrait of I.F. on the left. Semmelweis in the Hungarian national caftan. Next to the portrait, above the doctor's shoulder, is the date “1997” and the master's initials. To the right of the line dividing the obverse of the medal in half, the first and last name “SEMMELWEIS IGNÁC FULOP” and the dates of life are indicated -

“1818-1865” [33]. The reverse of the medal depicts the moment a doctor washes his hands. He washes his hands in a basin, the assistant pours water from a jug onto the doctor's hands. At the top of the reverse of the medal, there is an inscription in Latin “NIL NOCERE!”, which translates means “NOTHING HURTS!” [33].

Figure 28. Commemorative badge (medal), with a portrait of I.F. Semmelweis

Fig: 28. Shows a commemorative bronze breast badge (medal) of a participant in a medical conference in 1968 in Budapest, depicting a portrait of I.F. Semmelweis on the front of this token. The token has an eyelet for wearing on a block with a groove into which a piece of paper (cardboard) with the participant's surname and initials was inserted. The obverse of the

token features a portrait of I.F. Semmelweis and the inscription in Hungarian “Simmelweis Ignác Fülöp. 1818-1865”. On the reverse of this is the inscription “Septimana Solemnis; Semmelweis Budapest. 1968”, which translates to “Memorable Week. Semmelweis. Budapest. 1968”. The diameter of this bronze medal is 30 mm [34].

Figure 29. Clay medal dedicated to I.F. Semmelweis

Fig: 29 Shows a clay sketch of a bronze medal, on the obverse of which is a portrait of I.F. Semmelweis in the national Hungarian caftan, and on the upper hemisphere of the obverse the words in Hungarian “AZ ANYÁK

MEGMENTŐJE - SEMMELWEIS IGNÁC FÜLÖP.1818-1865” are minted [35].

Figure 30. Commemorative medal dedicated to I.F. Semmelweis

Fig: 30 Shows, on the obverse, another Hungarian bronze medal, with a portrait image of I.F. Semmelweis, face turned to the right. Along the entire

contour of the obverse of this medal, his first and last name and dates of life are given in Hungarian: "Semmelweis Ignác Fülöp. 1818-1865" [36].

Figure 31. Porcelain commemorative medal dedicated to I.F. Semmelweis

To complete the selection of commemorative medals, **Fig: 31** Shows an original porcelain, one-sided medal bearing on its obverse a portrait of I.F. Semmelweis, dressed in the Hungarian national caftan. The upper half sphere of this white porcelain medal is decorated with the inscription in gold

"SEMMELEWEIS IGNATZ. 1863" [37]. The unusual spelling of the doctor's name is noteworthy. Instead of the traditional "IGNAC" or "IGNAZ", or "IGNACZ", the spelling ends with the letters "TZ" [37].

Figures 32 and 32a. Placards dedicated to I.F. Semmelweis

Quite interesting are the silver plaques (not round medals) dedicated to I.F. Semmelweis, in which he is represented by bust-length portraits in his different age periods of life. On the poster **Fig: 32**. Under the portrait, a newborn child is depicted lying on a pillow, and on the second plaque **Fig.**

32a. Under the portrait of the scientist, two pregnant women are depicted talking, the object of the scientist's professional interest, and there are biographical data of the scientist [38].

Figure 33. Commemorative medal in honor of I.F. Semmelweis

Fig: 33. Shows, in obverse and reverse, a Hungarian commemorative bronze medal dedicated to I.F. Semmelweis [39]. On its obverse there is a head portrait of the scientist, turned to the left, his surname and first name "SEMMELEWEIS", and the dates of his life "1818-1865". The reverse of the

medal, large, is decorated with a stylized symbol of medicine - a snake entwined around a lit torch, with an open mouth, and decorated with laurel and plant branches [39].

Figure 34. Commemorative medal in honor of I.F. Semmelweis

In conclusion this article, in **Fig: 34**. The following commemorative bronze Hungarian medal is presented, also presented, in obverse and reverse, bearing the head portrait of I.F. Semmelweis, facing right, and his data written in Hungarian: "SEMMEWEIS IGNÁC FÜLÖP.1818-1865". The reverse of the medal has the inscription "A BUDAPESTI ORVOSTUDOMÁNYI EGYETEM REKTORA" across its entire field, which can be translated as "RECTOR OF THE BUDAPEST UNIVERSITY OF MEDICINE" [40].

This concludes another research commemorative article, thematically dedicated to the preservation of historical memory, about the famous scientist and obstetrician, I.F. Semmelweis. The author of this research article is preparing a continuation of his research, in the form of new articles devoted to the preservation of historical memory about I.F. Semmelweis, in numismatics - on commemorative coins, and also, in phaleristics, on thematic, commemorative signs and badges that will be published in the near future.

Conclusions

1. Modern means of collecting, in particular numismatics and phaleristics, to a significant extent, vividly and diversely represent various aspects of the biography, medical and scientific achievements of many heroes of world medicine.
2. The research materials presented in this article can be used for practical use when studying a course in the history of medicine in medical schools at various levels.
3. The author's use of this article, as 34 illustrations, screenshots, and commemorative tabletop medals (both color and black and white), thematically dedicated to the historical memory of I.F. Semmelweis.

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The author notes the complete absence of any conflicts, both with individuals and legal entities.